

IMTA Biofloc

PRODUCTION MANUAL

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SUMMARY

This manual was created as part of the WP2 'New IMTA value chains and production methods' of the H2020 All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture (ASTRAL) project. It provides detailed instructions of the cultivation technique for each of the species trialled at the ASTRAL IMTA labs. Three types of IMTA systems are included in this report, including an open-water IMTA system, a land-based pump ashore system and a IMTA Biofloc system. The ASTRAL species included fed and extractive species of fish, seaweeds, halophytes, molluscs, echinoderms and crustaceans.

Disclaimer: This material reflects only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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1. IMTA

IMTA is defined as the farming of aquaculture species from different trophic levels, and with complementary ecosystem functions in the same area or at the same site. This type of integrated culturing allows one species' uneaten feed, waste, and nutrients to be recaptured and converted into fertilizer and feed for the other aquaculture species. This approach takes advantage of synergistic interactions between species. The combination of fed aquaculture species (e.g., finfish or shrimp) with extractive aquaculture species, which utilizes the inorganic nutrients (e.g. seaweeds) and organic nutrients (e.g. suspension and deposit-feeders such as bivalves, urchins, sea cucumber) enhance growth in this type of system. IMTA aims to aid ecological balanced systems to improve environmental sustainability, enhance ecosystem services, boost economic stability by increasing biomass, lowering costs, providing product diversification, reducing risk, and creating jobs in rural communities while advancing societal acceptability¹.

¹ Chopin, T. (2013). Aquaculture, Integrated Multi-trophic (IMTA). In: Christou, P., Savin, R., Costa-Pierce, B.A., Misztal, I., Whitelaw, C.B.A. (eds) Sustainable Food Production. Springer, New York, NY. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-5797-8_173

2. ASTRAL PRODUCTION MANUAL

This manual contains detailed descriptions of the methods employed to produce the ASTRAL RAS with Biofloc species trialled in this research project. This manual will give guidance on how to grow the species and the parameters needed for their successful production, including welfare, health and biosecurity.

3. SOURCES OF INFORMATION ON IMTA PRODUCTION AND IMTA RESEARCH PROJECTS

ASTRAL H2020 project

<https://www.astral-project.eu/>

IMPAQT H2020 project

<https://impaqtproject.eu/about-impaqt/>

IMPAQT massive open online course (MOOC) in Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture and Precision Aquaculture

<https://www.open.edu/openlearncreate/course/view.php?id=7116>

AquaVitae H2020 project

<https://aquavitaeproject.eu/>

AquaVitae MOOC - Sustainable Aquaculture for Low Trophic Species

<https://open.uit.no/courses/course-v1:UiT+SALTS101+AquaVitae/about>

INTEGRATE project (INTERREG Atlantic Area 2014-2020 Programme) – Transition towards IMTA in the Atlantic Area

<https://integrate-imta.eu/>

IDREEM EU FP7 project – Increasing Industrial Resource Efficiency in European Mariculture

<https://www.bmrs.ie/bmrs-projects/past/idreem>

The Benefits of IMTA

IMTA benefits are environmental sustainability through bio-mitigation, economic stability through product diversification and, risk reduction and social acceptability through better management practices. IMTA may lead to increased biomass production, waste reduction, and new opportunities with regard to spatial use and species diversification.

The following are the benefits IMTA can potentially bring to a predominantly monoculture activity:

- Reduction in ecological impacts.
- From a linear to a more circular model, allowing for a whole ecosystem approach.
- “Waste” reduction service to the industry through bioremediation. The “wastes” become “co-products”, using the vocabulary of circular economy.
- Additional crops produced in IMTA (e.g., seaweeds) can be used as feed or feed ingredients for fed species, enhancing circularity and reducing feed costs.
- Inclusion of seaweeds in IMTA allows for increased recirculation and a reduction in pumping (electrical) costs.
- Full recirculation in IMTA can provide protection to farms during harmful algal bloom (HAB) events (by not pumping seawater from the adjacent ocean during HAB events).
- Seaweeds in IMTA systems or as a feed/aquafeed ingredients have a beneficial impact on the microbiome.
- Improving the societal perception of aquaculture.
- IMTA grown products may have a market advantage.
- Different IMTA models can bring different community benefits – such as with the re-stocking initiatives.
- Optimization of the space available, numerous products to be produced within the same space, utilising the resource effectively and efficiently.

- Commercial benefit from growing other products in their site.
- Diversity provides alternative incomes and cash-flows, increasing the resilience of the business.
- Beyond biomass – true value in added ecosystem services and nutrient trading credits that some low trophic species provide before being valued at the farm gate².

² Chopin, T., Costa-Pierce, B.A., Troell, M., Hurd, C.L., Costello, M.J., Backman, S., Buschmann, A., Cuhel, R., Duarte, C.M., Gröndahl, F., Heasman, K., Haroun, R.J., Johansen, J., Jueterbock, A., Lench, M., Lindell, S., Pavia, H., Ricart, A.M., Sundell, K.S., and Yarish, C., 2024. Deep-ocean seaweed dumping for carbon sequestration: questionable, risky and not the best use of valuable biomass. *One Earth* 7(3): 359–364.

The Challenges of IMTA

The challenges faced by IMTA production are largely economic and regulatory. Generally, there is an imbalance in income between the trophic layers and this can discourage the adaptation of the concept. Adding other trophic levels to monoculture set-ups increases the complexity of farm husbandry and infrastructure, and increases costs and efforts. Farmers are familiar with current systems and change is unattractive and can be risky.

Further research needs to be carried out to demonstrate that profits can increase compared to those of conventional production systems. Issues of awareness and education about these innovative production systems need to be addressed. Concerns around biosecurity when additional species are introduced, or when water is recirculated or co-products are returned to the systems as feed, need to be researched and assurance given to allow for increased societal acceptance of IMTA products.

Competition for space when low-trophic, lower value, species are introduced into systems can cause problems; however, the economic, biological and societal benefits of integration need to be demonstrated. The whole value of the IMTA production systems and the ecosystem services they provide have to first be recognized. This is the phase we are presently in. Next will be the valuation/monetarization of these services and their uses for regulatory and financial incentives to make aquaculturists, regulators, aquaculture practices and society evolve.

¹ Chopin, T. (2013). Aquaculture, Integrated Multi-trophic (IMTA). In: Christou, P., Savin, R., Costa-Pierce, B.A., Misztal, I., Whitelaw, C.B.A. (eds) Sustainable Food Production. Springer, New York, NY. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-5797-8_173

IMTA Biofloc System

The Federal University of Rio Grande (FURG) IMTA production system is situated in the southernmost region of Brazil (32°17'52.30" S – 52°15'59.80" W), experiencing a humid subtropical climate. This climate is characterized by hot, humid summers (with maximum temperatures reaching 40 °C) and cold (add minimum °C) to very mild winters, resulting in a relatively broad annual temperature range. The laboratory operates as a land-based IMTA system within a greenhouse, utilizing full recirculation approach and cultivating various species, including marine shrimps (*Penaeus vannamei*), tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*), oysters (*Crassostrea gasar*), halophyte (*Salicornia neei*) and macroalgae (*Ulva lactuca*). The super-intensive production in biofloc system serves as a sustainable and biosecure alternative to traditional intensive culture systems. Biofloc consists of uneaten feed, faeces, secretions, and their associated algal, bacterial, and microplankton communities.

Shrimp are cultivated in tanks at a high-density rate, exceeding conventional systems by 25 times, with a concentrated presence of water nutrients such as phosphates, nitrates, and organic matter—known as bioflocs in BFT system. To manage the elevated organic matter levels, tilapias are reared in separate tanks (Figure 1). Functioning as filter feeders, tilapias extract and consume bioflocs, repurposing the organic material within the production system. The nutrient-rich effluent water from the shrimp tanks is utilized as a food source for the fish, reducing the need for external feed inputs. The bioflocs and bacteria present in the system serve as supplementary feed for shrimps and an indirect source of nutrients for the plant and seaweed species.

Figure 1. IMTA system in Brazil. Consisting of just 3 tanks and a submersible pump to recirculate the water. No filters or other equipment to maintain water quality.

Water from the tilapia tank flows to another tank hosting seaweeds, which efficiently absorb dissolved nutrients, including reused nitrates and phosphates accumulated in the system. These seaweeds exhibit resilience to organic loads and capitalize on the transformation of nitrogenous compounds facilitated by bacteria present in the bioflocs. The blades of the seaweeds assimilate nitrogen compounds from fish and shrimp excretion, such as ammonia and nitrites, effectively removing and converting them into usable seaweed biomass.

The water from the primary tank, designated for shrimp production (Figure 2), is pumped into the fish tank. Through gravity, the effluent from fish production flows to the seaweed tank. Subsequently, the water returns by gravity to the main tank containing shrimps, completing the integrated and sustainable circulation within the production system.

Figure 2. Multi-trophic system (left) and shrimp tank with biofloc (brown water).

Considering the climatic variations in the southern region of Brazil and the unsuitable temperatures for tropical species (tilapia and marine shrimp) during autumn and spring, cultivation is carried out in greenhouses to extend the production period to 9-10 months/year. Table 1 shows the list of species trialled at IMTA lab Brazil.

Table 1. Species trialled at IMTA lab Brazil.

COMMON NAME	LATIN NAME	ROLE IN IMTA
White shrimp	<i>Penaeus vannamei</i>	Fed species
Tilapia	<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	Fed species
Native oyster	<i>Crassostrea gasar</i>	Extractive species
Seaweed	<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	Extractive species
Sea asparagus	<i>Salicornia neei</i>	Extractive species

The species at the IMTA lab Brazil are categorised as: fed and extractive species.

1. Fed species: The feed is used to grow shrimp and tilapia, but the fish are underfed and forced to eat biofloc. As a result, the animals release waste/nutrients into the water that is used as a nutrient source for the extractive seaweed species grown in the integrated system.

2. Extractive species: Dissolved nutrients are consumed by the seaweed *Ulva lactuca* and the organic material (biofloc) is controlled in the system by tilapias and oysters.

1. SPECIES PRODUCTION

Standard Operating Systems (SOPs) for all species here – refer to established industry protocols, if available.

1.1. MARINE SHRIMP (*Penaeus vannamei*)

- **Daily/Routine Operations**

The daily routine in shrimp production tanks consists of taking temperature, pH, and oxygen data in the early hours of the morning (7 a.m.). After these measurements, water samples are collected for daily analysis of ammonia and nitrite. Only after the water samples are collected do the animals receive their first feeding, provided that oxygen levels are within the pre-established limits.

Once this step is completed, the samples of ammonia and nitrite are analysed, and actions to be taken in case of values that may compromise the cultivation are determined. These actions may include adding a carbon source to reduce ammonia or, in cases of high nitrite values, possibly renewing the water.

New feeding should be carried out at the beginning of the afternoon (2 p.m.). However, there is no need to check oxygen and temperature parameters at this time if the values observed in the morning are at adequate levels. By late afternoon (5 p.m.), new temperature and oxygen

measurements should be taken to determine the total temperature variation in the cultivation tanks throughout the day. A final feeding should be provided in the evening (7 p.m.), concluding the daily feedings for the animals.

- **Feed & Nutrition**

As previously mentioned, daily feedings are conducted in three periods with commercial pellets. Regarding nutrition, juveniles weighing up to 0.4 g are provided with starter rations containing 40 % crude protein and fine particle size. Animals weighing between 0.4 and 1 g also receive rations with 40 % crude protein, but with a larger particle size. Once they reach 1 g, the transition is made to a 1.6 mm pellet size feed, maintaining the 40 % crude protein composition. This feed is utilized until the animals reach the desired size for commercialization. Being part of a biofloc system, the shrimp utilize the biofloc as a supplementary source of food, contributing to improved food conversion rates in cultivation.

- **Stocking Density**

The IMTA system, utilizing bioflocs, can accommodate stocking densities of up to 450 shrimp /m³, achieving a final cultivation productivity of 4.5 kg/m².

Regarding water quality parameters (Table 2), some values must be observed so that cultivation remains within acceptable levels for all organisms involved in the IMTA system. For shrimp, dissolved oxygen levels must be maintained above 5 mg/L. Extreme temperatures should be avoided, ideally maintaining the temperature in the range of 25 to 32 °C. Temperatures below this range lead to a reduction in the amount of feed to be offered to the animals, while temperatures above this range cause problems with dissolved oxygen, often making it impossible to offer the correct amount of food to the animals. The pH values must be maintained between 7.6 and 8.2 and the alkalinity above 150 mg/L of CaCO₃, mainly to enhance the action of bioflocs in the nitrification processes. Regarding Total Suspended Solids levels, these must be maintained in the range of 300 to 450 mg/L, an increase in this level of solids can lead to oxygen problems and also to the accumulation of organic matter at the bottom of the tanks.

Table 2. Optimal Environmental Ranges, oxygen, salinity, temp etc. for marine shrimp.

 Nutrients				
25-32 C	4-37	>5,0 mg/L	7,6-8,2	NH ₄ ⁺ < 1,0 mg/L NO ₂ ⁻ < 15,0 mg/L

Nitrogenous compounds must be kept at low levels, ammonia must be kept below 1 mg/L, nitrite below 5 mg/L. Nitrate values will only become a problem if the cultivation water is reused for several cycles, as the accumulation of this compound is slower in the system. Phosphate values in the biofloc system are typically maintained at or below 2 mg/L.

- **Record Keeping**

Water quality data are documented through manual methods, using paper spreadsheets that are subsequently digitized for long-term storage. These records serve as a valuable resource in the event of issues, capturing daily problems and documenting the measures taken to address them. This documentation becomes a vital reference for future problem-solving, particularly as work teams change over time. Additionally, automatic systems for measuring parameters such as temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, and total suspended solids are employed. Beyond recording variable values, these systems generate alarms when crucial cultivation parameters, like dissolved oxygen levels, experience significant drops.

- **Handling**

Minimizing animal handling is crucial to reduce stress associated with removal from and return to the water. In shrimp farming tanks, animals are handled only once a week, specifically for biometric measurements.

- **Growth monitoring**

Shrimp growth is evaluated on a weekly basis through biometric measurements. Randomly selected groups of 50 to 100 animals are individually weighed to determine the average shrimp weight (Figure 3).

Using this average weight, the total biomass of each tank is calculated. Subsequently, considering both the biomass and the environmental parameters of the cultivation, feeding rates for the upcoming week are meticulously calculated.

Figure 3. Shrimp sampling (left) and shrimp stocking in the tank (right).

- **Predator Control**

Predator control measures are deemed unnecessary in this cultivation system, given that it is conducted within a greenhouse environment. The greenhouse effectively prevents the presence of predators, ensuring a controlled and secure space for the animals.

- **Treatments**

No direct disease treatments are administered to shrimp in this cultivation system. Instead, preventive measures are implemented throughout the entire cultivation cycle. This involves the application of probiotics to establish a robust bacterial community that effectively excludes potential pathogens through competitive mechanisms.

- **Mortality Removal & Disposal**

Dead animals retrieved from the cultivation tank are frozen, and a specialized biological waste management company collects them at predetermined intervals. In the event of substantial mortalities, the collection of dead animals is conducted on demand.

- **Harvesting**

Shrimp harvesting includes both total and partial approaches. During total harvesting, water from the shrimp farming tank is drained—either by pumping or gravity—into a reservoir tank for subsequent reuse. The drained tanks retain shrimp in mesh nets suitable for their size, facilitating accurate weighing. Following weighing, the shrimp undergo a rapid chlorination process with a sodium hypochlorite concentration of 5 ppm. Subsequently, the animals are immersed in tanks containing fresh water and ice for quick cooling, preserving their quality. Once immobilized on ice, the shrimp are transferred to boxes, packed with ice, and swiftly transported to the fish processing plant.

For partial harvesting, small nets traverse the tank, selectively collecting a desired number of animals. This method is employed when animal growth rate decreases, indicating that the system has reached its support capacity. After removing a specified number of animals, the remaining shrimp resume growth until total removal is executed (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Marine shrimp production cycle consisting of a ca. 1 month hatchery phase followed by a 1 month nursery phase and 3 months grow-out phase.

1.2. TILAPIA (*Oreochromis niloticus*)

• Daily/Routine Operations

The daily operations in fish tanks closely parallel those for shrimp. This routine involves measuring temperature, pH, and oxygen levels in the early morning at 7 a.m. Following these measurements, water samples are collected for the daily analysis of ammonia and nitrite. The first feeding for the fish is scheduled only after the water samples have been collected, contingent upon oxygen levels falling within pre-established limits.

Upon completing this step, the ammonia and nitrite samples are analysed, and appropriate actions are determined in the case of values that could compromise the cultivation. These actions may include adding a carbon source to reduce ammonia or, in cases of elevated nitrite values, potentially renewing the water.

A second feeding is scheduled for the early afternoon at 2 p.m. However, there is no need to check oxygen and temperature parameters at this time if the morning values are within acceptable levels. By late afternoon at 5 p.m., new temperature and oxygen measurements are taken to assess the overall temperature variation in the cultivation tanks throughout the day. The final feeding for the fish is provided in the evening at 7 p.m., concluding the daily feeding routine.

• Feed & Nutrition

Daily feedings for fish occur in three periods. For fish weighing between 30 to 60 g, the rations have reduced protein content, ranging from 40 % to 36 %, with a pellet size of 3 to 4 mm. Juveniles weighing 1 to 5 g are provided with powdered starter feeds containing 40 % to 45 % crude protein. Fish weighing between 5 and 30 g receive rations with 40 % to 45 % crude protein, but with larger particle sizes, in the range of 1 to 3 mm pellet size. From 60 g to 250 g, the feed maintains an average of 32 % crude protein with a pellet size between 4 and 6 mm. Beyond 250 g, the feed contains 32 % to 26 % crude protein, with a pellet size of 6 to 8 mm. This feed is utilized until reaching the desired size for commercialization. In the BFT system, tilapia utilize biofloc as a supplementary food source, enhancing food conversion rates. The presence of biofloc allows tilapia to be fed with a maximum of 2 % of its biomass, whereas in a conventional system it would be 6%.

- **Stocking Density**

The IMTA system based on bioflocs can support stocking densities of up to 35 fishes per cubic meter, reaching a maximum system-supported density of 15 kg/m³.

Table 3. Optimal environmental ranges, oxygen, salinity, temperature etc. for Tilapia.

 Nutrients				
25-33 C	0-20	>4,0 mg/L	7,6-8,0	NH₄⁺ < 1,0 mg/L NO₂⁻ < 12,0 mg/L

As the water recirculates more than 100 % daily (300 L/h is the water pump flux), the parameters for fish are similar to those for shrimp (Table 3). Maintaining dissolved oxygen levels above 4 mg/L is crucial. It is advised to avoid extreme temperatures, ideally maintaining them in the range of 25 to 33 °C. Deviations from this range can impact feed consumption and dissolved oxygen levels. pH values should be kept between 7.6 and 8.0, with alkalinity above 150 mg/L of CaCO₃ to enhance biofloc action in nitrification processes. Total Suspended Solids levels must be maintained within the range of 300 to 450 mg/L, as an increase in solids can lead to oxygen problems and the accumulation of organic matter at the tank's bottom.

Nitrogenous compounds must be kept at low levels, ammonia must be kept below 1 mg/L, nitrite below 12 mg/L. Nitrate values will only become a problem if the cultivation water is reused for several cycles, as the accumulation of this compound is slower in the system. Phosphate values in the biofloc system are typically maintained at or below 2 mg/L.

- **Record Keeping**

Cultivation data are documented through both manual and automatic methods. Manual recording involves paper spreadsheets, later digitized for long-term storage, serving as a comprehensive record for troubleshooting. These spreadsheets capture daily issues and

document the measures taken to address them, providing a valuable reference for future problem-solving as work teams evolve over time. Automatic systems, measuring parameters such as temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, and total suspended solids, are also employed. Beyond recording variable values, these systems generate alarms in case of critical drops in vital cultivation parameters, such as dissolved oxygen levels.

- **Handling**

Minimizing animal handling is prioritized to mitigate stress associated with removal from and return to the water. In fish farming tanks, animals are handled every two weeks for biometric measurements only.

- **Growth monitoring**

Fish growth is monitored every 15 days through biometric assessments. Randomly selected groups of 20 to 30 animals are anesthetized and individually weighed to determine the average fish weight (Figure 5). From this average weight, the total biomass of each tank is calculated. Using this biomass and considering environmental parameters, feeding rates for the upcoming weeks are meticulously calculated.

Figure 5. Tilapia juvenile (left) and adult after harvest (right).

- **Predator Control**

Predator control measures are deemed unnecessary as the cultivation takes place inside a greenhouse, effectively preventing the presence of predators for these fish.

- **Treatments**

Due to constant recirculation, tilapia receive preventive treatment through the application of probiotics in the water. However, when they reach 30 g, the fish are vaccinated to minimize the risk of contamination by bacteria of the genus *Streptococcus*, known to cause significant mortality in unvaccinated fish farms.

- **Mortality Removal & Disposal**

Dead animals recovered in the tank are frozen, and a specialized biological waste management company collects them at predetermined intervals or, in the case of substantial mortalities, on-demand.

- **Harvesting**

As with shrimp, tilapia harvests can be total or partial. During total harvesting, water from the fish farming tank is drained, either by pumping or gravity, into a reservoir tank for subsequent reuse. The drained tanks retain the tilapia in mesh nets suitable for their size, facilitating accurate weighing. Following weighing, the tilapia undergo a rapid chlorination process with a sodium hypochlorite concentration of 5 ppm. Subsequently, the animals are immersed in tanks containing fresh water and ice for quick cooling, preserving their quality. Once immobilized on ice, the fish are transferred to boxes, packed with ice, and swiftly transported to the fish processing plant.

For partial harvesting, small nets traverse the tank, selectively collecting a desired number of animals. This method is employed when animal growth decreases, indicating that the system has reached its carrying capacity (15 kg/m³). After removing a specified number of animals, the remaining fish resume growth until total removal is executed, following the aforementioned procedure (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Tilapia production cycle consisting of a ca. 1-2 month hatchery phase followed by a 1-2 month nursery phase and 4-5 months grow-out phase.

1.3. SEA LETTUCE (*Ulva lactuca*)

- **Daily/Routine Operations**

The routine for tanks containing macroalgae differs from shrimp and fish tanks. As their role in the system is to absorb nitrogen and phosphate nutrients, feeding is unnecessary as these nutrients are dissolved in the cultivation water. The only daily activity involves gently moving the macroalgal biomass by hand to remove excess suspended solids deposited on them, enhancing light absorption throughout the day.

- **Feed & Nutrition**

As photoautotrophic organisms, macroalgae extract all necessary elements for growth directly from the cultivation water. Daily analyses of nitrogen and phosphate compounds assess nutrient availability for optimal growth. The system receives daily inputs of nitrogen and

phosphorous from feed and animal excreta. The bacteria in the bioflocs transform these compounds into products easily absorbed by the macroalgae, ensuring constant growth in the system.

- **Stocking Density**

The recommended initial stocking density for macroalgal biomass in the IMTA system with bioflocs is 1 g/L. This calculation should consider the entire volume of the production system, not just the tank where the macroalgae are placed.

Table 4. Optimal environmental ranges, oxygen, salinity, temperature etc. for sea lettuce.

|
Nutrients |
|---|--|--|---|---|
| 23-28 C | 20-35 | >5,0 mg/L | 7,5-8,2 | NH₄⁺ > 1,0 mg/L
NO₃⁻ > 10,0 mg/L
PO₄⁻³ > 8,0 mg/L |

Due to continuous water recirculation, macroalgae adapt to the physicochemical parameters specific to shrimp and fish (Tables 4). However, for proper development, the presence of nitrogenous compounds and phosphate is crucial, and the suspended solids should not exceed 350 mg/L to prevent significant shading and reduce growth rates.

- **Record Keeping**

Cultivation data are recorded manually using paper spreadsheets, later digitized for long-term storage. These records, capturing daily issues and measures taken to address them, serve as a valuable reference for future problem-solving, given changing work teams. Automatic systems measuring parameters such as temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, and total suspended solids are also used. In addition to recording variable values, these systems generate alarms in the event of a drop in vital cultivation parameters, such as dissolved oxygen levels.

- **Handling**

Daily handling of macroalgae involves gently shaking the biomass by hand during the morning routine to remove deposited material on the leaves. This process is conducted once a day, preferably in the morning, to maximize light incidence on the macroalgae's photosynthetic structures during periods of increased sunlight.

- **Growth monitoring**

Every 15 days, the growth of macroalgae is assessed (Figure 7). Cultivation structures containing the macroalgal biomass, initially weighed before the production period, are removed from the water. After a 15 to 20-minute period in the shade to drain excess water, these structures are weighed again. The difference between the current weight and the weight from 15 days ago provides the biomass growth during this period.

Figure 7. Seaweed in the system and after harvest.

- **Predator Control**

Predator control measures are unnecessary, as the cultivation takes place within a greenhouse, effectively preventing the presence of predators for these organisms.

- **Treatments**

No specific treatments are required for macroalgae. However, as they are integrated into the system, the same probiotic used for fish and shrimp is also present in the water and tank structures where the macroalgae are placed.

- **Mortality Removal & Disposal**

Macroalgae that present morphological abnormality or ghost tissues during cultivation are frozen, and a specialized biological waste management company collects them at predetermined intervals or, for significant mortalities, on-demand.

- **Harvesting**

Harvesting of macroalgae occurs throughout the production cycle. At each biometry assessment, biomass is removed to maintain it at 1 g/L, ensuring a consistent production of macroalgae biomass. This biomass can be stored fresh or dried and crushed for use in feed and food product formulations. At the end of the production cycle, all biomass is harvested and utilized for various purposes as outlined above.

1.4. SEA ASPARAGUS (*Salicornia neei*)

- **Daily/Routine Operations**

The routine of halophyte production in PVC NFT hydroponic benches is divided into two stages: 1st water quality analysis and 2nd maintenance of the structures. In the first stage, water samples are collected daily from each aquaponic bench at two specific points: the inlet and outlet water of each IMTA system, respectively, in the shrimp tank and in the return pipe of the bench. As for the second stage of structure maintenance (aquaponic bench), the flow and water flow (average flow rate 455.3 L/h) passing through the benches are checked daily, as well as identifying possible leaks and water passage obstructions. The plants are constantly irrigated with water from the shrimp culture biofloc, resulting in biofloc accumulation in the channels of the aquaponic benches. Weekly washings of the structures are necessary with the aid of a hose to remove excess solids and prevent both channel obstruction and water overflow. The drained solids were returned to the shrimp raceways (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Accumulation of solids on the benches, and on the roots of the plants, being removed with the assistance of a hose.

- **Stocking Density**

The IMTA systems are connected with a aquaponics system arranged with PVC nutrient film technique (NFT) growing *S. nei* halophytes, positioned on the exterior side of the greenhouse (Figure 9). Each aquaponic bench has 6 tubes measuring 85 mm X 45 mm and 3 m in length (area = 4.8 m²), containing 19 plants in each tube and a total of 114 plants per bench (6 benches = 684 plants).

Figure 9. Layout of the PVC aquaponic benches, installed outside of the greenhouse.

The water quality parameters for *Salicornia neei* are the same as those for shrimp farming, with the parameters of greatest interest for plant growth being phosphate and, especially, nitrate concentrations, which should be above 10 mg/L (Table 5). Low nitrate concentrations can be a limiting factor for plant development, as well as low solar radiation. Air temperature in this region varied between 9.0 and 32.5 °C (average = 22.0 ± 0.4 °C) in summer, and the maximum solar radiation is 3.9 J/m²/s (3900 W/m²; average daily radiation = 17.87 ± 0.76 MJ/m²/d).

Table 5. Optimal environmental ranges for sea asparagus.

 Nutrients				
25-32 C	4-37	>5,0 mg/L	7,6-8,2	NH ₄ ⁺ < 1,0 mg/L NO ₂ ⁻ < 15,0 mg/L

- **Record Keeping**

The collected data, both on water quality and biometrics, are recorded on printed spreadsheets and later digitized for analysis and monitoring of the system's development. This proves crucial for identifying potential irregularities and applying necessary corrections to maintain the proper functioning of the experimental units. The printed spreadsheets are archived and accessed when needed for any record-related queries.

- **Handling**

Daily handling of the plants is minimal, except when pruning is necessary for biometric analysis.

- **Growth monitoring**

The plant growth is assessed through pruning, carried out every 30 days of cultivation. During each pruning, all *S. neei* plants on the benches are identified and cut 4 cm above the upper edge of each cup (Figure 10A and B).

Following pruning, the fresh above ground biomass of each plant (stems with branches) is measured using a precision scale (Figure 10C). The fresh root biomass of each plant, which grows outside the cups, is quantified only at the end of the experiment, also through weighing on a scale. In each experiment, the stem and root biomasses of 10 plants from each bench are dried in an oven (60 °C for 48 h) and weighed on a precision scale, allowing for the calculation of dry biomass (Figure 11A-D). Stem succulence is estimated by the percentage difference between fresh and dry biomasses. The percentage of biomass allocated to stems (aboveground biomass) is estimated by dividing the stem biomass values by the total biomass formed (stems + roots) and multiplying by 100. Biomass production per bench area is also estimated by summing the individual biomasses of all plants on the bench and then dividing this value by the bench area (4.8 m²). Additionally, the stem height (in cm) and the number of branches exceeding 10 cm in length for each plant are quantified (Figure 10D).

Figure 10. Harvesting of *S. nei* plants. (A) Pruning of plants, keeping the stem at cup height. (B) Collection and storage in bags for analysis of plant samples in the laboratory. (C) Weighing of fresh biomass. (D) Stem biometrics of the plants.

Figure 11. Assessment of dry biomass produced by *S. nei* plants. (A) Detail of stems and roots of plants on drying trays. (B) Drying of biomass samples in the oven. (C) Weighing and (D) storage of the dried material.

- **Mortality Removal & Disposal**

In the current cultivation, the average survival rate ranged from 91 to 85 %. Plants considered dead are discarded as organic waste.

- **Harvesting**

Harvests are carried out based on biometrics, with all plants being harvested every 30 days. *Salicornia neei* is a perennial plant capable of regrowth from its stem after pruning. All plants are weighed and measured to assess growth and productivity indices, and then distributed for consumption among the academic community at the Marine Aquaculture Center.

1.5. BRAZILIAN NATIVE OYSTER (*Crassostrea gasar*)

- **Daily/Routine Operations**

The routine for the tanks where the oysters, which are sessile filter-feeding organisms, are housed consists mainly of daily visual inspections of the structures containing these animals. This is done to assess the presence of dead animals, which need to be removed, as well as any potential damage to the cultivation structures.

- **Feed & Nutrition**

As oysters, being filter-feeding organisms and being part of a cultivation environment with bioflocs, utilize these bioflocs, which are abundantly present throughout the entire cultivation period, as food no limitation of the growth of these organisms has been observed. By removing the bioflocs for feeding, the oysters fulfill their role as biological control of total suspended solids levels (Figure 12).

- **Stocking Density**

The recommended stocking density for oysters in the IMTA system with bioflocs is 10 individuals/m³. This may vary depending on the volume of the system being used.

For proper development, temperatures higher than 28°C should be avoided, and the suspended solids should not exceed 250 mg/L, considering the production in BFT system (Table 6).

Table 6. Optimum environmental ranges for the Brazilian native oyster.

 Nutrients				
20-28 C	18-37	>5,0 mg/L	7,4-8,2	TSS <250 mg/L

- **Record Keeping**

Cultivation data are initially recorded manually using paper spreadsheets and later digitized for long-term storage. These records document daily observations and actions taken to address any issues, serving as valuable references for future problem-solving, especially considering changes in work teams. Additionally, automatic systems measuring parameters such as temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, and total suspended solids are employed. Apart from recording variable values, these systems also generate alarms in case of any significant deviations in vital cultivation parameters, such as dissolved oxygen levels.

- **Handling**

The daily management involves removing the cultivation structures from the water and analyzing the integrity of the structures as well as the presence of dead oysters, which need to be removed to prevent degradation of water quality.

- **Growth monitoring**

Every 30 days, shell length measurements are taken to assess oyster growth. The average value is then subtracted from the previous average value to establish the average growth over the period.

Figure 12. Production of Brazilian native oyster – *Crassostrea gasar*.

- **Predator Control**

Predator control measures are unnecessary, as the cultivation takes place within a greenhouse, effectively preventing the presence of predators for these organisms.

- **Treatments**

No specific treatments are required for oysters. However, as they are integrated into the system, the same probiotic used for fish and shrimp is also present in the water and tank structures where the oysters are placed.

- **Mortality Removal & Disposal**

The oysters that die during cultivation are frozen, and a specialized biological waste management company collects them at predetermined intervals or, in the case of significant mortalities, upon request.

- **Harvesting**

The harvesting of oysters occurs at the end of the cultivation cycle (Figure 13), and the oysters can be sold while still fresh.

Figure 13. Oyster production cycle consisting of a ca. 1 month hatchery phase followed by a 2-3 weeks settling phase and 8-10 months grow-out phase.

2. HEALTH

Health assessments are conducted during the handling of animals, seaweeds and plants integrated into the system, following the guidelines drawn up by the Brazilian Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock. For shrimps, observations include checking for necrosis in appendages and the animal's body, greening of the uropod (indicative of possible vibriosis – Figure 14), and examining the filling of the digestive tract and hepatopancreas to gauge proper feeding. In fish, assessments focus on the presence of white dots on the body, the normal appearance of eyes, absence of abdominal dilation, cleanliness of gills, and the absence of materials or parasites. For macroalgae, whitish blades may indicate light issues or nutrient deficiencies. Any reported problems prompt the collection of animals, seaweeds or plants for more detailed histology and biochemistry analyses to accurately identify and address underlying issues.

Figure 14. Problems that can be observed in the IMTA tanks. Shrimp with necrosis (black spot – left), shrimp with *Vibrio* (blue-green animal – centre), seaweed with ghost tissues (right).

The Ministry of Aquaculture and Fisheries is the main authority for the management and development of fisheries and aquaculture in Brazil. Alongside the Federal District, the States and Municipal Authorities, and the Ministry of Aquaculture and Fisheries are responsible for the granting of licences and permits for aquaculture. The Institute of the Environment and Renewable Natural Resources (IBAMA) is concerned with the environment and deals with conservation of natural resources (including aquatic resources), environmental licences and water quality

control³. Regarding the seaweed and halophytes health, no regulations were established in the country.

³ https://firms.fao.org/fi/website/FIRetrieveAction.do?dom=legalframework&xml=nalo_brazil.xml#tcNB0076

3. BIOSECURITY

Biosecurity measures within the system are highly effective due to its closed greenhouse environment. All circulation openings are equipped with screens to prevent the entry of birds, known carriers of pathogens. The closed doors also prevent access by other land animals. For water, in the case of initiating cultivation without water reuse, all pumped water undergoes chlorination. After chlorine removal, probiotics are applied to stimulate the colonization of known and fast-growing bacteria, excluding potential pathogens through competition. Upon arrival, all animals and plants undergo a quarantine period to assess the presence of diseases or parasites that could pose problems during cultivation. Subsequently, animals are transferred to production units. Regular visits by the responsible veterinarian are conducted to evaluate animal health and ensure adherence to animal welfare protocols.

4. WELFARE

The recirculation system's inherent characteristics may lead to occasional imbalances in variables for the species involved. Continuous analyses over time have demonstrated that, despite the high densities and potential turbidity, no stress factors were observed in the cultivated animals. This indicates that the system provides an environment where animal welfare is maintained in equilibrium, fostering significant growth rates and high survival rates compared to other farming systems.

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